

Microwave Induced Stereoselective Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of β -Lactams

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The compounds containing quinoline ring have been found to exhibit broad range of biological activities¹. The discovery of penicillins and cephalosporins focussed the attention of synthetic chemist on β -lactam ring. The contribution of Bose *et al.*² in microwave assisted synthesis of 2-azetidinones prompted us to synthesize a new series of *trans*- β -lactams³ using MORE (microwave induced organic reaction enhancement) chemistry.

2-Hydrazino-4-methylquinoline was treated with substituted aryl aldehydes to get the corresponding hydrazones. The hydrazones on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of a base afforded β -lactams. Conventional as well as microwave heating were used in two different experiment for synthesis of β -lactams (Schemes 1 and 2). The compounds (**5a-h**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2. Method A : $\text{ClCOCH}_2\text{Cl}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$, room temperature, 5–11 h. Method B : $\text{ClCOCH}_2\text{Cl}/\text{NMM}/\text{chlorobenzene}$, MWI, 5–8 min.

Results and Discussion

All the β -lactams were synthesized using conventional as well as microwave heating. The ir band of **5a-h** at 1740 cm^{-1} is characteristic of β -lactam carbonyl. The stereochemistry of the β -lactams was resolved through ^1H nmr spectral data. The β -lactams exhibited two doublet (J 1.8–2.5 Hz) due to hydrogen atom at C-3 and C-4. The coupling constants for H-3 and H-4 (J 1.8–2.5 Hz) indicate

trans-stereochemistry of β -lactams⁴.

Compounds **5a-h** were screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The filter paper disc method⁵ was employed using ethanolic solution of the compound at concentrations 25 and $50\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Ampicillin was used as reference drug. *In vitro* studies showed antibacterial activity against species *E. coli*, however, these compounds exhibited only moderate activity against *S. aureus*. Compound **5b** showed activity comparable to ampicillin.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded on a Thomas Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R32 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Elemental analyses were performed on a Heraeus CHN-Rapid analyser. The purity of the compound was achieved through column chromatography.

4-Methylcarbostyryl (**1**) was prepared by treatment of acetoacetanilide with sulphuric acid⁶. 2-Hydrazino-4-methylquinoline were obtained from 2-chloro-4-methylquinoline⁷ according to the reported method⁸.

The hydrazones (4a-h). General procedure : A mixture of 2-hydrazino-4-methylquinoline (**3**; 10 mmol) and aromatic substituted aldehyde (10 mmol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 3–5 h. The excess of solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the resultant solid was heated with water. The separated solid was crystallised from ethanol.

β -Lactam (5a-h). General procedure. Method A : To a stirred solution of the hydrazone (**4a-h**) and triethylamine (molar ratio 1 : 6) in anhydrous dichloromethane (3 ml/mmol of hydrazone) at room temperature, was added dropwise a solution of chloroacetyl chloride (1.2–2 mol/mol of hydrazone) in the same volume as above of the dry dichloromethane. After stirring for 5–8 h at room temperature, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, diethyl ether added to the residue, and the precipitate filtered off. Removal of the solvent from the filtrate gave a residue which was purified by column chromatography over

silica gel and CHCl_3 -EtOAc as solvent system and recrystallised from proper solvent.

Method B : To a solution of hydrazone (37 mmol) in chlorobenzene (5 ml) was added successively *N*-methylmorpholine (75 mmol) and chloroacetyl chloride (47.5 mmol) in Erlenmyer flask (500 ml). The flask was capped with a glass funnel and placed in a microwave oven. A beaker (500 ml) containing water (150 ml) was placed in the oven next to the reaction flask to serve as a heat sink. The mixture was irradiated for 5–8 min under low power setting. The approximate temperature of the reaction (110–120°) was determined by using a thermometer after the microwave irradiation was stopped. After the usual work up, desired β -lactam (**5a-h**) was isolated : **5a** (61%), m.p. 58° (Found : C, 67.43; H, 5.10; N, 12.35. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{OCl}$ requires : C, 67.55; H, 4.73; N, 12.44%); ν_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.50 (3H, s, 4- CH_3), 3.5 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, 4-CH), 4.4 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, 3-CH), 6.6–7.8 (10H, m, ArH), 9.6 (1H, br, NH); **b** (48%), m.p. 43° (Found : C, 61.45; H, 4.04; N, 11.32. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{OCl}_2$ requires : C, 61.29; H, 4.63; N, 11.29%); ν_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.70 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 3.9 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 4-CH), 4.7 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 3-CH), 6.7–7.9 (9H, m, ArH), 9.8 (1H, br, NH); **c** (55%), m.p. 55° (Found : C, 68.32; H, 5.30; N, 12.25. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{OCl}$ requires : C, 68.27; H, 5.13; N, 11.93%); ν_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.60 (6H, s, 2 \times CH_3), 3.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 4-CH), 4.5 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, 3-CH), 6.5–7.8 (9H, m, ArH), 10.1 (1H, br, NH); **d** (65%), m.p. 81° (Found : C, 64.85; H, 5.20; N, 11.28. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 65.31; H, 4.90; N, 11.43%); ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.75 (3H, s, 4- CH_3), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.1 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, 4-CH), 4.9 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, 3-CH), 6.75–7.2 (9H, m, ArH), 10.1 (1H, br, NH); **e** (41%), m.p. 65° (Found : C, 59.52; H, 4.22; N, 14.45. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 59.61; H, 3.93; N, 14.64%); ν_{max} 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.7 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 3.85 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, 4-CH), 4.55 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, 3-CH),

6.75–7.5 (9H, m, ArH), 9.9 (1H, br, NH); **f** (45%), m.p. 92° (Found : C, 62.57; H, 4.45; N, 11.32. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 62.99; H, 4.20; N, 11.02%); ν_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.7 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 3.85 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 4-CH), 4.6 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 3-CH), 5.8 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.1–8.3 (8H, m, ArH), 9.8 (1H, br, NH); **g** (35%), m.p. 88° (Found : C, 63.85; H, 4.82; N, 16.10. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}$ requires : C, 63.81; H, 4.44; N, 16.54%); ν_{max} 1725 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ 2.75 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 3.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 4-CH), 4.65 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 3-CH), 6.5–8.1 (9H, m, ArH), 10.0 (1H, br, NH); **h** (62%), m.p. 52° (Found : C, 67.25; H, 4.32; N, 14.72. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}$ requires : C, 67.11; H, 4.25; N, 14.91%); ν_{max} 1740 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.8 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 4.1 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 4-CH), 4.9 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 3-CH), 6.5–8.1 (10H, m, ArH), 9.6 (2H, br, NH).

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